

Motivation in Human Resource Management

İnsan Kaynakları Yönetiminde Motivasyon

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ABSTRACT

The link between Human Resources Management and motivation is a critical element that shapes the process of businesses effectively managing employees. Human resources management includes strategies and practices to increase employee commitment to work, optimize their performance, and direct them towards business goals. This study will reveal that highly motivated employees make positive contributions by focusing on the direct impact of motivation on business performance.

Human resources and motivation management can face various challenges. The responsibility of managing various employee profiles can complicate the process of determining motivation strategies. Motivation differences between individuals are also a challenge. Businesses need to adapt their general motivation strategies to individual needs. Diversity and equality issues should also be addressed. Wage inequality and inequality in career opportunities can cause motivation losses.

Human resources and motivation are key elements for businesses. However, to implement this management effectively, it is important to adopt an approach that is compatible with diversity and equality principles. Considering the importance of motivation in business life, the diversity and equality-oriented implementation of human resources and management is indispensable for the success of businesses and employee satisfaction.

Keywords: Human Resources, Motivation, Organizational Success

ÖZET

İnsan Kaynakları Yönetimi ve motivasyon arasındaki bağ, işletmelerin çalışanları etkili bir şekilde yönetme sürecini şekillendiren kritik bir unsurdur. İnsan kaynakları yönetimi, işe çalışanların bağlılığını artırmak, performanslarını optimize etmek ve onların işletme hedeflerine yönlendirmek amacıyla strateji ve uygulamaları içerir. Bu çalışma motivasyonun iş performansına doğrudan etkisi üzerinde durarak, yüksek motivasyona sahip çalışanların olumlu katkı sağladığını ortaya koyacaktır.

İnsan kaynakları ve motivasyon yönetimi çeşitli zorluklarla karşılaşabilir. Çeşitli çalışan profillerini yönetme sorumluluğu, motivasyon stratejilerini belirleme sürecini karmaşılaştırabilir. Bireyler arasındaki motivasyon farklılığı da bir zorluktur. İşletmelerin genel motivasyon stratejilerini bireysel ihtiyaçlara adapte etmeleri gereklidir. Çeşitlilik ve eşitlik sorunları da ele alınmalıdır. Ücret eşitsizliği ve kariyer fırsatlarındaki eşitsizlik, motivasyon kayıplarına neden olabilir.

İnsan kaynakları ve motivasyon işletmeler için kilit unsurlardır. Ancak, bu yönetimi etkili bir şekilde uygulamak için çeşitlilik ve eşitlik prensipleriyle uyumlu bir yaklaşım benimsemek önemlidir. İş hayatında motivasyonun önemini göz önüne alarak, İnsan kaynakları ve yönetiminin çeşitlilik ve eşitlik odaklı uygulanması, işletmelerin başarısı ve çalışan memnuniyeti açısından vazgeçilmezdir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İnsan Kaynakları, Motivasyon, Organizasyon Başarısı

INTRODUCTION

The rising trend of human resources management and talent, which is seen as an element that gives businesses a competitive advantage, is usually an innate power. Potentially expressed as 'the ability to do', talent represents a concept related to behavior. With the disappearance of boundaries in business life, advancing information and technology are shaping a dynamic business life. Talent management, which emerged in this process, aims to employ the right employee at the right time and place. The ability of businesses to make a difference depends on their effective use of human resources today, and for this reason, talent management has an important position both in business life and among academic studies.

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With the effects of globalization, in the "information age" where change is experienced rapidly, businesses have focused on new and creative initiatives that will differentiate them from their other competitors against customers. It has been understood that creativity can emerge through human capital and can be provided by talented personnel. For this reason, businesses aim to gain competitive advantage by focusing on processes such as attracting talented personnel to the business, placing them in the job, making evaluations, implementing career management and retaining personnel.

In today's business world, the most important factor in organizations gaining and maintaining competitive advantage is human resources management strategies. In this context, motivation, which stands out among the factors that determine the performance of businesses, has the potential to direct and influence the behavior of employees. Human resources management must go beyond traditional functions such as recruitment and performance evaluation and adopt strategic approaches that will strengthen the motivation of employees. In this context, the purpose of this study has been determined as examining the effects of human resources management on motivation in depth and understanding the strategic practices of businesses in this area. The main objective of the study is to understand the role of motivation in the workplace, evaluate the methods used in this regard, and present an analysis supported by qualitative and quantitative data on how businesses can be optimized to increase their competitive advantage. It should also be noted that this research aims to fill the knowledge gap on how businesses can develop customized motivation strategies that are suitable for their culture and consider the individual needs of employees. In this context, the study aims to offer new perspectives on how motivation, a critical factor for corporate success, can be strengthened through Human Resources Management strategies.

HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

Human resources management is the process of hiring, training, developing, motivating and evaluating a sufficient number of qualified personnel to perform the functions required for businesses to achieve their goals (Human Resources Management includes a series of strategic and operational functions aimed at effectively managing human resources for organizations to be successful. These basic functions reflect the purpose of Human Resources Management to help the organization achieve its goals by using its human resources in the best way possible. Human Resources Management manages these functions in an integrated manner to contribute to the overall success of the business as a strategic partner.

The Human Resources function is a comprehensive function that aims to manage, develop and protect the employees, who are the most valuable assets of an organization. The Human Resources function plays an important role in the process of achieving business goals as a strategic partner. Human Resources functions have different but mutually supporting stages (Zaim & Polat, 2013).

The recruitment function is perhaps one of the most important functions. Because placing the right potential person in the right job also ensures that the employee's motivation is high. Recruitment includes the process of finding, evaluating and selecting individuals with the qualifications the organization needs. Recruitment is a critical step for the long-term success of the organization and includes a series of goals such as selecting the right candidate, increasing performance, ensuring workforce diversity and strengthening business culture (Kaynak, 1996).

Training and development in the recruitment process plays a critical role in organizations effectively integrating new employees and developing the skill sets necessary for long-term success. Training and development activities should not be considered as a result to be achieved, but as an important tool used by organizations to achieve their strategic goals (Şimşek & Serdar, 2007). By supporting the personal and professional development of employees, organizations are enabled to maintain their competitive advantage and adapt to the changing business environment. This process can be managed using training programs, seminars, mentoring and various learning resources, which positively affects job performance by increasing employee motivation and commitment (Kuşluyan, 1999).

During the application collection phase, it is also important to provide candidates with a process where they can easily apply and communicate with the organization. In this way, creating and publishing an effective advertisement is a fundamental step for organizations to attract suitable candidates and successfully manage the recruitment process (Dülek, 2018).

The application evaluation phase allows organizations to make an important distinction between candidates before taking any further steps. Candidates determined based on the evaluation results usually proceed to the interview phase. At this stage, organizations can conduct more detailed and in-depth evaluations. Application evaluation is one of the cornerstones of an effective recruitment process because it is critical for organizations to select the most suitable candidates and manage the process efficiently (Barutçugil, 2006).

The interview process plays a critical role in further distinguishing between candidates and determining the most suitable candidates. Organizations have the opportunity to understand the motivations, commitment to the job, and long-term goals of candidates through interviews. At the same time, they also can evaluate important aspects of candidates such as problem-solving abilities, communication styles, and crisis management skills. The interview process represents a critical stage in the process of selecting qualified and suitable candidates for organizations and should be carefully planned and managed in order to successfully complete the recruitment process (Özden, 2008).

Reference checking during the recruitment process represents a critical stage for organizations to learn more about potential candidates and evaluate their past work performance. This process is carried out through solid references about candidates' previous work experience, leadership teamwork, communication skills, and overall work performance. This process evaluates the candidate's previous work experience and achievements in a real-world context, helping to select a candidate that fits the organization's needs. In addition, feedback obtained through references provides important insights into the candidate's suitability for the organizational culture and long-term success potential (Erol, 2021; Özgen & Yalçın, 2012).

The offer stage during the recruitment process symbolizes the stage where the organization formally initiates a collaboration with the candidate it has identified. At this stage, the successfully evaluated and selected candidate is given a formal job offer for the position. It is important to ensure clear and open communication between both the organization and the new employee at all stages of the recruitment process. This helps both the organization and the new employee meet their expectations and start a collaborative relationship (Özgen & Yalçın, 2012).

Feedback is an important element for both the organization and the candidate. Regularly informing candidates about where they are in the recruitment process and the steps, they can expect helps candidates better understand the process and have a more positive experience. Monitoring and feedback processes allow organizations to continuously make improvements to ensure that the recruitment process is transparent, effective and candidate friendly.

Training and Development

Training and development, which are often used together, are “any initiative or action to improve the current and future performance of the employee by increasing their ability to do their job effectively.” In other words, training and development are “an effort planned by the organization to facilitate learning job-related behaviors for the employee.”

Planning and implementing training programs to increase employees' abilities, knowledge levels, and skills are among the responsibilities of Human Resources. This contributes to the career development of employees and adapts to the changing needs of the organization (Şimşek & Serdar, 2007). In addition, performance improvement strategies are one of the basic elements of Human Resources Management. These strategies support efforts to achieve set goals, increase employees' abilities, and strengthen the company's competitive advantage. Human Resources support the long-term success of the company by ensuring the effective implementation of these processes (Özgen & Yalçın, 2012).

Increasing employees' motivation, ensuring job satisfaction, and strengthening their commitment are important tasks of Human Resources. This includes managing motivational elements such as reward systems, personal rights, and career development opportunities. The functions of human resources management are the sum of activities aimed at increasing the effectiveness of human resources and therefore the organization (Yüksel, 1998).

Human Resources encourages effective communication in the workplace and strengthens relationships between employees. Problem solving, supporting teamwork, and conflict management play an important

role in this context. The Human Resources Department regulates relationships between employees, resolves conflicts, and develops policies to strengthen work relationships. This helps maintain a positive atmosphere in the work environment (Yüksel, 1998).

The human resources department determines the requirements of positions by conducting job analysis. The results of job analysis form the basis for planning, including job descriptions, position requirements, and skill profiles. In addition to the definitions given above, job analysis can be defined as the process of collecting and examining all information related to the responsibilities of a particular job and the procedures for doing that job (Yıldız, 1989).

Human Resources Principles

To create correct and consistent policies for implementation, there are some basic principles that all administrative structures must follow. Although these principles vary according to the structures and goals of the businesses, they aim to guide the relevant units in order not to cause chaos in working life and to achieve goals. Human Resources Management also includes compliance with ethical standards and social responsibilities. Respecting the rights of employees, encouraging diversity and justice, and adopting sustainable business practices are all parts of the ethical and social responsibility understanding of Human Resources.

There are six basic principles in Human Resources Management. These are equality, assurance, efficiency, competence, career, and openness. These principles reflect the basic values and goals of Human Resources Management and support fair, safe, efficient and effective human resources management in organizations. Human Resources principles are the basic principles that serve the purpose of effectively managing and developing the employees of a business. By adopting these principles, businesses can increase employee satisfaction, increase productivity and achieve sustainable success (Tuna, 2013).

Human Resources should strive to ensure fair treatment and equal opportunities in recruitment processes. It is important to adopt a zero-tolerance principle against discrimination, support diversity, and provide objective evaluations for candidates. While correct decisions made during recruitment positively affect the performance of human resources managers and the organization, incorrect recruitment decisions negatively affect performance and cost the organization dearly (Mentor, 2009).

Human Resources management should ensure that employees are objectively evaluated with an effective performance evaluation process. These evaluations should be conducted regularly to determine the strengths and development areas of employees. These objective performance evaluations provide the opportunity to provide employees with rewards in line with their achievements. Recognizing achievements increases employee motivation and creates a competitive advantage within the company. This both strengthens employee loyalty and supports a culture of rewarding success in the company culture (Budak, et al. 2017).

Human Resources should offer various programs and opportunities to support employees' career development and provide continuous training opportunities. A career trajectory should be drawn. Functional characteristics of positions should be determined, jobs that are similar in practice should be grouped together and logical connections should be established between these jobs. Career consultants should be assigned. Individual plans should be developed. After career trajectories are created and jobs are grouped together, individual plans of employees should be prepared and developed (Özgen & Yalçın, 2012).

Human Resources management should take effective measures to protect the health and safety of employees. In this context, it is of great importance to develop specific policies and processes to ensure full compliance with occupational health and safety standards. Effective implementation and monitoring of these policies is also of great importance. Ensuring advanced occupational health and safety has become one of the top priorities in all advanced countries (Tüzüner, 2008).

Human Resources management should strengthen cooperation among employees by encouraging transparent and effective communication. Being sensitive to feedback from employees, evaluating this feedback and improving business processes both increases employee satisfaction and contributes positively to the overall performance of the company (Karsantik & Erol, 2021; Esen, 2011). In addition

to keeping communication channels open, conflict management is also one of the basic duties of Human Resources. Early detection of possible conflicts, finding objective solutions between the parties and supporting cooperation ensure that the department operates successfully. Human Resources should mediate conflict situations and find fair solutions and contribute to maintaining a positive work environment among employees.

Employee satisfaction is referred to as “job satisfaction” or “job satisfaction” in scientific literature and emerges because of the employee’s personal evaluation of working conditions (Telman, 2004). Ensuring employee satisfaction can help organizations not only retain their workforce but also increase productivity and job performance. Therefore, determining and developing the factors affecting job satisfaction is an important responsibility of Human Resources management. Human Resources management plays a key role in adhering to ethical standards and adopting fair business practices. This includes making objective evaluations of employees based on their abilities, performance and potential. Another important principle that Human Resources must adhere to is full compliance with laws and regulations. Transparency and honesty principles increase trust among employees and strengthen the reputation of the company (Telman, 2004: 126).

Human Resources management increasingly understands the importance of encouraging diversity and valuing different talents, cultures and perspectives in today's business world. Therefore, Human Resources departments should develop effective strategies to increase and maintain diversity in the workforce. The second basic principle of Human Resources is to encourage everyone's participation by creating an inclusive work environment. This means providing equal opportunities, ensuring justice and maximizing the potential of employees. Human Resources departments can strengthen this inclusive work environment by adopting transparent and open communication policies, valuing employees' ideas and respecting different perspectives (Öğüt, et al. 2004). These Human Resources principles can help businesses achieve sustainable success and manage their human resources effectively. These principles can build trust among employees, enhance the reputation of the business, and provide a competitive advantage.

MOTIVATION

One of the most important ways to get full efficiency from employees is to provide work motivation. Because only highly motivated employees are willing and diligent to do their jobs in the most perfect way. This situation creates a positive atmosphere in the work environment and also helps employees to be much more peaceful. The people who need to provide employee motivation are managers (Karakoç, 2021).

Motivation in human resources management is a key element in increasing employees' performance, strengthening job satisfaction and ensuring that they focus on business goals. In addition, human resources management's efforts to strengthen motivation contribute to creating a stable workforce by reducing turnover rates. In this way, human resources management effectively implements its strategies aimed at creating a positive work environment within the organization and increasing success at individual, team and organizational levels.

Types of Motivation

Types of motivation are listed as extrinsic motivation, intrinsic motivation, positive motivation, negative motivation, basic motivation, social motivation, ego-centered motivation, task-oriented motivation, and daily motivation (Çalışkan, 2021). Human Resources Management uses various extrinsic motivation elements to encourage employees and increase their performance. Among these elements, financial rewards play an important role. Praise for employees' success can positively affect both individual and teamwork performance.

In addition to extrinsic motivation elements, it is important for Human Resources to focus on intrinsic motivation factors. Intrinsic motivation elements such as employees' satisfaction with their jobs, their passion for their jobs, and personal development opportunities can support long-term commitment and success. In order to achieve this balance, Human Resources should focus on both the effective use of financial rewards and strategies that support job satisfaction and intrinsic motivation (Aslan & Doğan, 2020).

The role of Human Resources in encouraging employees to take more responsibility for their jobs and to take part in creative projects is also important. By interacting more with their jobs and supporting participation, employees can feel more passion and commitment to their jobs. This both increases individuals' intrinsic motivation in line with their personal goals and makes a positive contribution to the company's overall efficiency and innovation capacity (Aslan & Doğan, 2020).

Career development is another important factor that helps employees achieve their personal and professional goals. Human Resources can support employees in developing their skills and climbing their career ladders by using tools such as training programs, mentoring and career planning. By emphasizing these positive elements, Human Resources supports positive motivation, which both increases employee satisfaction and has a positive impact on the company's overall performance (Koçel, 1998). It can focus on motivating employees with performance-based reward systems and work-life balance strategies. Such positive methods can increase employees' intrinsic motivation, while contributing to long-term commitment and productivity. Adopting such strategies by Human Resources can help prevent negative motivation, as well as create a sustainable and healthy work environment (Çalışkan, 2021).

Human Resources Management includes motivation strategies aimed at basic needs, and these strategies aim to meet employees' basic needs such as salaries, occupational safety and health. At the same time, Human Resources Management aims to increase the quality of work life by expanding strategies to meet employees' basic needs by ensuring occupational safety and health. Providing a safe work environment makes it easier for employees to focus on their work and increases their motivation. Human Resources protects the physical and mental health of employees by implementing measures such as occupational safety training, risk analyses, and regular health checks, thus supporting their general motivation by meeting their basic needs (Çalışkan, 2021).

Workplace communication is also an effective tool for increasing social motivation. Human Resources regularly creates in-workplace communication strategies, encouraging employees to exchange ideas and share their opinions. These social motivation strategies of Human Resources both strengthen relationships in the workplace and increase employees' commitment to their work, encouraging productivity (Koçel, 1998).

Human Resources Management can develop strategies that support ego-centered motivation to strengthen individuals' desire for personal success and recognition. Human Resources' success-oriented motivation strategies include various mechanisms to recognize and reward employees' contributions. Methods such as performance-based bonus systems, employee of the year awards, and achievement certificate applications are effective tools to meet employees' desire for personal success and recognition. These strategies both make individuals feel valued and can increase overall performance by creating a motivational environment focused on success in the company culture (Koçel, 1998).

By supporting task-oriented motivation, human resources management enables employees to focus on their work and duties. It implements task-oriented motivation strategies with tools such as career development, training and performance evaluation (Çalışkan, 2021). Task-oriented motivation stands out as an important strategy in the context of motivation. Human resources departments use various tools to encourage employees to focus on their work and duties.

Human Resources' efforts to improve business processes and communication can make it easier for employees to communicate and cooperate effectively in daily work conditions. A good communication and cooperation environment allows employees to get along better with each other, solve problems and increase their motivation. The adoption of these strategies by Human Resources can strengthen both employee satisfaction and the company's overall performance, thus contributing to a more positive daily work environment (Bayar, 2019).

Factors that Motivate People

The main factors that provide work motivation are wage, job characteristics, working conditions, career opportunities, hierarchical structure, job security, organizational culture. Working in repetitive jobs will cause the individual to get bored at work. Boredom can lead to psychological problems such as depression, loneliness, hopelessness and absent-mindedness in the individual (Farmer & Sundberg,

1986). These factors are the basic elements that affect the motivation of employees in a workplace. The material gains obtained at work directly affect the motivation of employees. A sufficient and fair wage ensures that the employee is more committed to his/her job. Wage is an important factor in meeting the basic living needs of employees. A sufficient wage is necessary for employees to continue their daily lives and meet their basic needs. A reasonable wage level can increase employees' job satisfaction and commitment to the workplace. This can make employees tend to stay in the company and be more committed to their jobs (Balta, 2007).

Employees want their jobs to be interesting, challenging and meaningful. The nature of the job, the variety of tasks, the level of responsibility and the general meaning of the job affect employees' motivation. Employees' understanding of the meaning of their work and feeling that their work serves a purpose can increase their motivation (Bayar, 2019). The work environment, working conditions and physical environment affect employees' commitment to their work. Working conditions include physical, psychosocial and organizational elements in a workplace. These conditions have a significant impact on how employees perceive their jobs, their performance and motivation. A positive work environment and company culture can enable employees to be more committed to their jobs and increase their motivation (Ünsar, et al. 2010).

Employees' career opportunities include how they can develop their careers, advance and gain new opportunities in an organization. Employers can develop various strategies and practices to support employees in their career development and communicate opportunities within the company (Ünsar, et al. 2010). The management and leadership style in the workplace, the hierarchical structure, affects the motivation of employees, but this effect depends on many factors. Good leadership, fair practices, open communication and career development opportunities can increase motivation within the hierarchical structure. Organizations should try to maximize motivation by creating a hierarchical structure that suits the needs and expectations of employees. Fair leadership and open communication can make employees feel valued (Alamur, 2005).

Employees want to know that their jobs are secure. Job security provides employees with an emotional sense of trust and job stability. This can contribute to employees having a certain assurance about their future, which can positively affect their motivation. Employees with job security can take risks and participate in innovative projects without worrying about losing their jobs. Job security can encourage employees to be more open to developing their careers and trying new things (Bayar, 2019). Organizational culture refers to a common understanding of an organization's shared values, beliefs, norms, behaviors and work styles. Organizational culture includes the basic elements that shape the way employees work together, strategies to achieve goals, and the work environment. This culture has a significant impact on employee motivation (Alamur, 2005).

Organizational culture is a basic element that represents the existence and working style of an organization. This culture determines the character of the organization through shared values, beliefs, norms, and work styles.

The Effect of Motivation on Job Performance

Motivation is the desire of a person to do a job. In this sense, high performance cannot be expected from an individual who is not well motivated. Determining which motivational factors can motivate the employee is one of the most important criteria for high motivation and performance (Salihoğlu, 2020).

In addition, low motivation levels can negatively affect job performance. Lack of motivation can lead to results such as dissatisfaction with work, low energy levels, and indifference towards work. Low motivation can reduce productivity at work, increase the tendency to leave work, and weaken employees' emotional commitment to their jobs. Therefore, it is critical for employers to develop strategies to increase employees' motivation for long-term success and sustainable job performance (Salihoğlu, 2020).

APPLICATIONS OF HUMAN RESOURCES UNITS TO INCREASE MOTIVATION

The relationship between Human Resources Management and motivation plays an important role in creating a healthy and productive work environment in the business world. Human resources management covers the process of managing employees, the most valuable assets of businesses, and this

process includes a series of strategies that affect the motivation of employees. Motivating employees can increase job performance, increase job satisfaction, and contribute to a positive atmosphere in business life in general.

The effective implementation of human resources management emphasizes that managers should encourage a culture focused on open communication, fair leadership, and cooperation. When employees feel valued at work, they tend to increase their performance. Businesses can design their human resources management strategies to support motivation, ensuring that employees are passionate and committed to their work. As a result, this mutual relationship between human resources management and motivation contributes to businesses achieving sustainable success and employee satisfaction.

Motivation-Focused Human Resources Practices

Motivation-focused human resources practices aim to ensure that employees feel more committed to their jobs, increase their performance, and contribute more effectively to the company's overall goals (Yargül, et al. 2021). Performance evaluation and feedback refers to the process by which an organization evaluates the performance of its employees and provides feedback on this performance. This process is implemented to support the development of employees, help them achieve goals, and ensure that they contribute to the company's overall success. Performance evaluations are an important tool for highlighting strengths and identifying areas for development (Yargül, et al. 2021).

Reward systems are strategic approaches that an organization implements to motivate its employees, encourage their performance, and ensure that they achieve certain goals. These systems aim to recognize, reward, and encourage employees' specific achievements or contributions. Reward systems can generally include methods such as recognition and appreciation, as well as material and moral rewards. Incentive systems such as performance-based awards, bonuses, and recognition awards encourage employees to put in effort. These awards can increase motivation by rewarding employees who achieve goals (Yargül, et al. 2021).

Businesses can offer training and development programs to help employees develop their skills. A creative and learning-friendly work environment can increase employee motivation. Training and development programs play an important role in ensuring that employees develop their skills, have up-to-date information about their jobs, and maximize potential within the company for long-term success (Yargül, et al. 2021). While training and development programs strengthen employees' skills, a creative work environment can also increase motivation. These programs help maximize potential within the company by providing the necessary information to adapt to changing conditions at work.

Career planning and promotion opportunities include strategies designed for employees to manage, develop, and advance their careers within the company. Effective management of these issues can increase employee motivation and contribute to long-term company success. In addition, career planning and promotion opportunities can increase employees' commitment to the company and encourage them to focus on long-term goals. Opportunities and open communication within the company allow employees to focus on their career development (Yargül, et al. 2021).

Flexible working hours, remote working opportunities, and policies that support work-life balance can positively affect employees' motivation by improving their overall quality of life. Considering that everyone reaches their biological clock and peak productivity at different times, flexible working hours can allow employees to focus on the hours when they are more productive. This can lead to a higher level of efficiency and quality of work during work hours. However, it should not be forgotten that flexible working hours can also include some challenges in addition to the advantages they bring. It is important to consider issues such as communication problems, team coordination, and collaboration difficulties (Yargül, et al. 2021).

Regular communication between managers and employees, bilateral meetings aimed at understanding and solving problems, can strengthen employees' emotional commitment to their jobs. These practices constitute the basic strategies of human resources management and provide an effective framework for businesses to increase their motivation with the support they provide to their employees. In this way, businesses can achieve sustainable success and gain competitive advantage (Yargül, et al. 2021).

Obstacles to Increasing Motivation

Human Resources Management and effective management of motivation can face a number of challenges. Human resources management is responsible for managing a wide range of employees with different expectations, abilities and motivation levels. This heterogeneous structure can complicate the process of determining and implementing motivation strategies. At the same time, global work environments that bring together employees from different cultures can present additional challenges in understanding motivation and meeting everyone's needs.

Another important challenge is the differences in motivation factors among individuals. The factors that trigger motivation for each employee are different, and a general motivation strategy may not effectively cover all employees. Human resources management should be careful to understand individual needs and create personalized motivation plans. In addition, changing work environments and expectations over time can lead human resources management experts to constantly revise and update motivation strategies. In this context, human resources management and motivation management should be a dynamic and adaptive process, but the complexity of this process presents challenges to managers and human resources management professionals (Şimşek, 2023).

Recommendations for Human Resources Units to Increase Motivation

Human Resources Management and motivation cover an area shaped by the challenges faced in terms of diversity and equality issues. These issues play a critical role in ensuring a fair environment in the workplace. Wage inequality, especially differences seen on the basis of gender, ethnicity or age group, can lead to loss of motivation among employees. Subjecting employees with equal skills to different wages in the same position damages the perception of justice at work and reduces motivation.

Inequalities in access to career development opportunities can also negatively affect motivation. The fact that a certain group of employees have more promotion and advancement opportunities than others can deepen diversity problems and increase general employee dissatisfaction. The perception of diversity and the atmosphere in the workplace also affect employees' commitment to their work. If the workplace does not adopt a diverse structure or does not value the differences among its employees, this can negatively affect motivation.

In addition, negative behaviors such as discrimination and harassment can create an environment in the corporate culture that does not encourage diversity and equality, thus reducing employee motivation. Such situations can create a sense of insecurity in the workplace and undermine employees' commitment to their work. Ignoring cultural differences can make team harmony difficult in the workplace, which can lead to problems with cooperation, communication, and motivation.

Managing human resources and motivation in a way that is sensitive to diversity and equality issues contributes to the creation of a fair work environment and the development of effective strategies to increase employee commitment to work. By understanding these challenges, creating a culture that embraces diversity, and implementing policies based on the principle of equality, businesses can provide a motivating work environment. Each employee's motivational sources are different and it is difficult to constantly monitor employee motivation. It is necessary to develop personalized motivation strategies and constantly evaluate these strategies (Şimşek, 2023).

CONCLUSION

The link between Human Resources Management and motivation represents a vital element that embraces the process of businesses effectively managing employees and encouraging them to perform at the highest level. Human resources management includes a series of strategies and practices aimed at increasing employees' commitment to work, optimizing their performance, and directing them towards business goals.

Given the fact that motivation is a critical factor that directly affects business performance, the role of human resources management becomes even more important. Highly motivated employees make a positive contribution to the workplace with their commitment, energy, and focus on their work. Human resources management includes various strategies to strengthen and sustain this positive impact. These strategies include elements such as recruitment, training, performance evaluation, career planning, and rewards.

However, human resources management and motivation management can face a number of challenges. The responsibility of businesses to manage a heterogeneous employee base can complicate the process of determining motivation strategies. Global business environments that bring together employees with different expectations, abilities, and motivation levels can create additional challenges in understanding motivation and meeting everyone's needs. Human resources management experts should adopt a careful and original approach to cope with this diversity and develop an effective motivation strategy.

Another important challenge is the difference in motivation factors among individuals. Businesses should be careful to go beyond developing a general motivation strategy and understand individual needs and create personalized motivation plans. Human resources management and motivation management is a dynamic and variable process, and it is important for businesses to adapt quickly to these changes and achieve long-term success.

In addition, human resources management and motivation should also address the challenges associated with diversity and equality issues. Various factors, such as wage inequality, inequality in career development opportunities and discrimination, can lead to loss of motivation among employees. The efforts of human resources management experts to positively affect motivation by creating a work environment focused on diversity and equality are critical for long-term sustainable success.

As a result, human resources management and motivation represent key elements for the success of businesses and sustainable performance. Highly motivated employees provide commitment, energy and focus in the workplace, which contributes to the achievement of the business's goals. However, Human Resources management and motivation management may face various difficulties; managing an employee base with different expectations and cultures, individualizing motivation strategies and adopting a sensitive approach to diversity issues are important in order to overcome these difficulties. Considering that motivation plays such a critical role in business life, the implementation of human resources management by blending it with diversity and equality principles is indispensable for the success of businesses and employee satisfaction.

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